

Suitable Partner Selection and Resource Allocation in Cooperative Wireless Communication using the Trade-Off game

Authors : Oluseye Adeleke and Mohd. Fadzli Mohd. Salleh

Abstract : The performance of any cooperative communication system depends largely on proper allocation of resource like power. Another important factor to consider is the selection of a proper partner by the source node to help it in forwarding information to the destination. In this paper, we look at the concepts of partner selection and resource allocation for a distributed communication network. A type of non-cooperative game referred to as Trade-Off game is employed so as to jointly consider the utilities of the source and relay nodes, where in this case, the source is the node that requires help with forwarding of its information while the partner is the node that is willing to help in forwarding the source node's information, but at a price. The approach enables the source node to maximize its utility by selecting a partner node based on (i) the proximity of the partner node to the source and destination nodes, and (ii) the price the partner node will charge for the help being rendered. Our proposed scheme helps the source locate and select the relay nodes at 'better' locations and purchase power optimally from them. It also aids the contending relay nodes maximize their own utilities as well by asking proper prices. Our game is also seen to converge to the unique equilibrium.

Keywords : cooperative communication, game theory, node, power allocation, trade-off, utility

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